

Methodologic assessment of brake-by-wire system modelling with regard to accuracy, model complexity and optimization efforts

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Abstract

Brake-by-wire systems are an innovative and important component of modern high-performance and also electrified vehicles. Due to their decoupled architecture, they enable driver-independent vehicle dynamics control (e.g., brake torque blending) and easy integration of assistance functionalities (e.g. Emergency Brake Assist (EBA)). On the other hand, the development of these functions can cause high costs and development effort, and testing can be critical in case of improper gain tuning. Therefore, already in the concept phase, a large part of the testing is shifted to virtual environments and simulations that allow safe and reproducible experiments without damage. Therefore, suitable and reliable models are needed to represent reality as accurately as possible.

This paper deals with the modelling of a purely electrohydraulic brake-by-wire system and a hybrid system with electrohydraulic brakes on the front axle and electromechanical brakes on the rear axle. For comparison, both an experimental approach based on a second-order transfer function and an analytical model are used. These approaches are then evaluated in terms of their accuracy and reliability using real measurements in different dynamic test setups. Finally, it is shown how accurate the approaches are and what advantages can be achieved by using the different methods for system modelling.

Introduction

Modern vehicles are becoming more and more complex due to the constantly increasing number of embedded systems and functions, which is also caused by an ongoing trend of vehicle electrification and automation. Especially in the area of X-by-wire applications (e.g. brake-by-wire (BBW)), this trend poses a major challenge due to several aspects. The first relates to the fact that purely electric chassis systems without any physical fallback level place higher demands on functional safety, as described in [1]. The second challenge is that X-by-Wire systems are mechatronic systems which include mechanical and electrical hardware parts as well as control software. Since the usual development approaches are structured in-line (e.g. VDI 2221) or iterative (e.g. VDI 2206 “V-model”) with separate development loops for each part, prototypes are not available until quite late. In addition, the parts often have to be adapted for different vehicle models or variants. Depending on the ratio between both, see Fig. 1, several prototypes are necessary throughout the development process.

Figure 1. Comparison of the ratio between the number of variants and the number of baseline models for different car manufacturers

To speed up this process, virtual product development strategies are increasingly used. By replacing real hardware with models, some important decisions and refinements can be made at early stages of development, saving costs and additional iterations of redesign. In addition, the models can be used for re-engineering and developing future systems, e.g. with improved packaging, dynamics, safety, etc.

There are several proven methods for modelling dynamic systems such as multi-body simulations, finite element or finite volume analysis, process simulation, co-simulation, etc. [2]. The choice of the method to be used depends strongly on the purpose of the simulation. In addition, some of the approaches require more preparation and computing power than others. However, the data for the models are derived from physical phenomena, mechanical interactions or structural analyses in all cases. By combining these expressions, the overall function is replicated. Because of the algebraic formulae, this approach is often called *analytical modelling*. [2]

This approach is advantageous for investigations into new architectures and subcomponents. Depending on the level of detail, conclusions can be drawn immediately about any change and appropriate decisions can be derived. Especially in the case of automotive brake systems, various aspects must be taken into account in early development phases. For example, the thermal behavior in the friction zone between brake pad and disc is highly non-linear and temperature-dependent. Mechanical design, thermal management and alternative disc/lining materials can positively influence this behavior to avoid overheating of the brake. In most cases, computational fluid dynamics simulation [3, 4], finite element analyses [5, 6, 7] or mathematical models [8, 9] are used.

In addition to the purely mechanical and thermal aspects, the design of the control software is also a thoroughly relevant aspect that could benefit from model-based development. Especially in the context of automated driving, safety and assistance functions, virtual development is advantageous for several reasons. The use of detailed models of the target hardware enables the development of control algorithms through model-in-the-loop (MIL) and software-in-the-loop (SIL) methods. Once the prototype is available, worthwhile time of gain scheduling can be saved by proper pre-tuning. In addition, the experiments cannot cause any harm, because the tests are purely virtual. However, these methods require accurate virtual models with a clearly defined level of detail.

In [10, 11], the approach was used to validate BBW functions with emphasis on characterizing the system behavior. In [12], the performance of the magnetorestrictive brake actuation concept was tested in a simple vehicle dynamics simulation using a two-degree-of-freedom bicycle model. The results were compared with a coupled hydraulic brake system, although no further details of its architecture or type were given. In [13], the modelling of an electromechanical brake for use in electric vehicles is presented. The detailed model was used to investigate the performance/dynamics for different parameter settings. In [14], a vacuum boosted hydraulic brake system was modelled to develop and optimize a sliding mode control for braking torque generation. In all listed publications the software Matlab®/Simulink® was used.

Another case study was proposed in [15], where the benefits of an electrohydraulic brake system in terms of improved vehicle handling, pedal feel and comfort were demonstrated through virtual experiments in a non-hazardous environment. In addition, a new control algorithm for BBW systems was investigated in [16]. In both cases, the Siemens AMESim software was applied, which allows the use of pre-configured blocks that already contain the analytical model. This procedure facilitates the simulation setup, as the time-consuming modelling of algebraic equations is not necessary. On the other hand, the user can only adjust the inputs and outputs, but has no insight into the equation(s), so it is more difficult to consider simplifications or linearization.

If there are physically existing components or even the whole target system, an experimental modelling approach can be proposed. For dynamic identification, the system is excited with an input signal (e.g. steps, ramps, sine) and the output is measured. From these data, a transfer function is derived that simulates the system behavior based on a single formula. This strategy is useful when no technical data is known or when the focus is on benchmarking tests. It is also beneficial for reverse engineering applications. For example, this approach was used in [17] for rapid control prototyping (RCP) for several use cases on different vehicles with the same braking system.

It can be seen that the strategy often has to be tailored to the specific use case. The analyzed publications show different methods for specific use cases, but often lack details about the modelling effort or even the model accuracy. For this reason, this paper deals with a comparative study of BBW modelling of two different system architectures. Therefore, the architecture of the braking systems, the modelling and the experimental validation are discussed in the following sections.

Brake System Architecture

General brake-by-wire system architecture

In general, any automotive braking system includes the driver-brake interface (DBI) with brake booster, the main caliper, the transmission parts (fluid lines, cables), the calipers and the brake discs. The latter can also be replaced by drum brakes, but these are not considered in the selected BBW systems. In addition, modern brake systems are equipped with at least one electronic control unit and electronically controlled valves that realize functions such as anti-lock braking system (ABS), electronic stability programme (ESP) and electronic brake force distribution (EBD). In BBW systems, the physical link between the driver and the braking system is severed. Driver inputs are measured by redundant displacement sensors and pressure sensors (e.g. to detect emergency braking) and transmitted to the control unit, where the braking torque requirement is calculated and then distributed to the corners. In general, three BBW system concepts are known with electrohydraulic brakes (EHB), electromechanical brakes (EMB) and hybrid forms that use both principles. Since pure EMB systems are currently not used due to the high safety requirements for functional safety, see [1], EHB and hybrid systems are the preferred principles. Therefore, two of these brake-by-wire systems are investigated. One is a purely electrohydraulic BBW system, while the other has a hybrid structure. The following sections describe their architecture and functions.

Electrohydraulic brake-by-wire (EH-BBW) system

The first system, as introduced in Fig. 2, has been previously studied by the authors of this paper, in cooperation with industrial partners, in the European project E-VECTOORC.

Figure 2. Scheme of the first analyzed system [17]

This system includes a multi-chamber main caliper with two brake circuits, as required by [19]. Its architecture implements a classical axle split, i.e. the first brake circuit includes the left and right front wheels, the second circuit the left and right rear wheels. Since the vehicle is mainly designed for electrified vehicles (BEV, PHEV), a

vacuum booster is missing. Alternatively, the pedal feel in normal operation is emulated by a haptic simulator that works with mechanical springs and brake fluid ("wet simulator"). It is part of the electrohydraulic control unit (EHCU). This package also includes the brake control unit (BCU), which generates the brake pressure demand based on the information from the displacement sensor, and controls the electromagnetic valves to modulate the brake pressure at each wheel (e.g. during operation of ABS). In addition, the valves allow blending of the braking torque between the friction and regenerative braking systems. In [17, 18] the potential of the system for blended operation has already been shown. In the event of a failure or malfunction (e.g. power loss), the valves connect the brake pedal directly to the brake calipers to ensure a deceleration of at least 0.25g according to [19]. In order to be able to react to rapidly occurring ramps, a pressure accumulator stores the brake fluid under high pressure between 140bar and 180bar. It is driven by a pump that is supplied by the 12V battery. This central unit is advantageous in terms of system packaging and integration, as it can be mounted freely in the front of the vehicle and does not require a direct connection to the master cylinder.

Hybrid brake-by-wire (H-BBW) system

The second system was adopted from the authors' earlier studies in [20] in collaboration with industrial partners in the European project EVC1000. It has a hybrid structure: the front axle is equipped with electrohydraulic actuators (EHAs) connected to the calipers and the rear axle is equipped with EMBs with integrated electronic parking brake (EPB). The architecture realizes an axle split, which makes the system fail-safe, e.g. in case of power failure, as the normally open valve (NO) is opened and the master cylinder is then directly connected to the front brakes. Furthermore, by reducing the number of hydraulic connections and parts, the required amount of brake fluid is reduced, which has a positive effect on environmental friendliness. Fig. 3 shows a schematic representation of the brake system.

Figure 3. Scheme of the second analyzed system.

In by-wire mode, the valve NO is closed and the master cylinder is directly connected to the pedal simulator, so that the driver receives force feedback by compressing a damping element in the simulator. The pedal travel is measured by two redundant sensors and the signal is transmitted to the vehicle control unit (VCU). There, a braking torque demand for both axles is calculated and forwarded to the two BCUs, which generate the necessary actuator signals for brake pressure (front) or clamping force (rear). Also for this system, some

earlier performance investigations have already been outlined and presented in [20].

Modelling Methodology

As described in the Introduction section, there are several approaches to system modelling in general. In this paper, a comparison of the *transfer function* (TF) and also the *analytical model* (AM) for the above mentioned braking systems will be carried out. For this purpose, tests were done on the physical hardware, which serve as a reference for the model validation described later. Therefore, the test benches from Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 are used. Both test benches are equipped with processing hardware from dSPACE GmbH. A Simulink® model, which handles both signal generation and distribution, is compiled in C code for this purpose, then downloaded to the dSPACE system and then processed in real time. A DS1006 processing unit (not shown in Fig. 4) is used for the EH-BBW, while the H-BBW is controlled by a processing unit from the latest product series (SCALEXIO) with a high-performance Intel XEON® processor.

Figure 4. Test bench set-ups for the electrohydraulic BBW system

Figure 5. Test bench set-ups for the hybrid BBW system

Experimental approach

After the description of the braking systems and the test environment, the next sections deal with the modelling process and validation. First, the experimental approach is discussed. For characterization, the system is excited with one or more specific input signals ($u(t)$) and the output ($y(t)$) is measured. The transfer function is defined as $y(t)/u(t)$. In the present case, the braking demand from the simulation is the input, while the real measured braking pressure (EH-BBW) or braking torque (H-BBW) is the output. A mixture of step, sawtooth

and sinusoidal signals was used to excite the system. In a next step, a practicable structure must be chosen. The system EH-BBW can be expressed by a second-order transfer function, see [17]. Since it is generated by discrete measured values with fixed sampling time, the z -transformation is used instead of the continuous-time approach. The corresponding structure is given by Eq. (1). The constant of the numerator (b_0) describes the direct connection between input and output. It must be equal to zero so that the output signal cannot perform any steps. This approach was already investigated in [23] and showed reliable results.

$$G(z) = \frac{b_0 + b_1 z^{-1}}{1 + a_1 z^{-1} + a_2 z^{-2}} \quad (1)$$

The discrete transfer functions are shown in Table 1 and Table 2 and were calculated by the *System Identification Toolbox* from Matlab®.

Table 1. Transfer function of all corners on the EH-BBW system

	$G(z) = \frac{b_1 z^{-1}}{1 + a_1 z^{-1} + a_2 z^{-2}}$		
	b_1	a_1	a_2
FL	4.5365×10^{-4}	-1.9692	0.9697
FR	4.0576×10^{-4}	-1.9711	0.9715
RL	6.3271×10^{-4}	-1.9625	0.9632
RR	6.4141×10^{-4}	-1.9625	0.9632

Table 2. Transfer function of all corners on the H-BBW system

	$G(z) = \frac{b_1 z^{-1}}{1 + a_1 z^{-1} + a_2 z^{-2}}$		
	b_1	a_1	a_2
FL	8.8449×10^{-4}	-1.9522	0.9531
FR	7.8386×10^{-4}	-1.9557	0.9565
RL	7.8772×10^{-4}	-1.9517	0.9525
RR	8.2202×10^{-4}	-1.9528	0.9536

It can be seen that there is no directly derivable relationship between the coefficients and the parameters of the braking system, i.e. adjustments to the system (e.g. variation in line lengths, fluid density, etc.) cannot be readily applied to the mathematical expression without new measurements and system identification following the changes. Therefore, a different type of modelling is now discussed.

Analytic approach

Another way of modelling dynamic systems is the analytical approach, in which the behavior of the components (e.g. valves, fluid dynamics, etc.) is represented by algebraic expressions. Due to the complexity of the system, only a brief insight into some relevant parts is given here. The complete analytical model, based on the work in [22], is presented in [23, 24].

First, some basic elements will be introduced. Since the system uses electromagnetic valves to modulate and distribute the brake pressure at all corners, a description is mandatory. In the simplest case, a valve can be described as a limitation of the volume flow Q

$$Q = \dot{V} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\zeta}} A_V \sqrt{2 \frac{|\Delta p|}{\rho}} \text{sign}(\Delta p) \quad (2)$$

where ζ is the resistance factor, depending on the valve cross-section A_V and the Reynolds number, Δp is the pressure gradient in front of and behind the valve, ρ is the fluids density. The sign function at the end indicates, if the flow is forward or reverse.

Next phenomenon to investigate is the pressure in the hydraulic lines. Due to the continuous filling with a changing amount of brake fluid, given by the volumetric flow between inlet (\dot{V}_1) and outlet (\dot{V}_2), they can be modelled as temporary volume accumulators. The more brake fluid is stored in these accumulators, the higher the pressure. The pressure change depends on the hydraulic capacity C_{fl} , as the ratio of the available volume V and the fluids' compressibility module K .

$$p = \frac{1}{C_{fl}} \int_t \Delta \dot{V}_{21} dt = \frac{V}{K} \int_t \dot{V}_2 - \dot{V}_1 dt \quad (3)$$

As described and outlined in Fig. 2, a high-pressure accumulator (HPA) is also used to store braking pressure for rapidly occurring pressure gradients (e.g. ABS). Technically, it is a steel housing with a nitrogen-filled gas bubble inside. The more liquid is added, the more the gas bubble is compressed and the higher the stored pressure. A valve controls the volume flow. The pressure is then represented by the following expression

$$p_{fl}^{k+1} = p_{fl}^k \left(\frac{V_{HPA,max} - V_{fl}^k}{V_{HPA,max} - V_{fl}^{k+1}} \right)^n \quad (4)$$

where $V_{HPA,max}$ is the maximum storable volume in the HPA, V_{fl}^k is the stored fluid volume at the time step k and n is the polytropic exponent. The pressure gradient, necessary for filling the HPA is realized by an electrically driven fluid pump. The mechanical power P_{mech} , needed for the filling process, can be calculated as follows

$$P_{mech} = P_{hydr} \quad (5)$$

$$M_m 2\pi n_m = \Delta p \lambda_p n_m V_H$$

where M_m is the motor torque, n_m is the rotational speed, λ_p is the pump efficiency and V_H is the amount of volume to be changed. Since the data of the motor/pump was not available, they were determined in an iterative process.

Fig. 6 shows the brake caliper model from [24]. It considers caliper movements x_C when brake pressure is applied. Moreover, the brake piston (mp) is moved by the brake pressure, generating the hydraulic force F_{hydr} on its cross-section area, giving a more accurate model than the simplified one-mass oscillator from [22, 23].

Figure 6. Brake caliper model used for simulation

The low-level control of the system is divided into three parts: Pressure modulation and allocation (primary), HPA re-filling (secondary) and assist control to prevent excessive pressure gradients between the boost valve and the hydraulic circuit (tertiary). Since all valves are probably controlled by pulse width modulation (PWM), which is difficult to model without further knowledge, a different approach was chosen. Considering the maximum frequency of the valves of 50 Hz, see [22], a logic in Simulink[®] allows new signals only in fixed time steps of 0.02s. Table 3 lists all model parameters as far as they are known. The parameters marked with *) were either estimated or derived from the literature and the technical specifications of the component suppliers.

Table 3. Model parameters for the EH-BBW system.

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Value
Valve cross section (inlet / outlet)	A_V	mm ²	27.8 / 1.4
Resistance coefficient *) (forward / reverse)	ζ	-	5 / 2.5
Fluid density	ρ	kg/m ³	900
Fluid compressibility module	K	bar	60
Polytropic exponent (filling / extracting)	n	-	1 / 1.4
Working pressure (HPA)	p_{HPA}	bar	140 - 180
Max. volume	$V_{HPA,max}$	cm ³	120
Initial pressure (nitrogen)	p_{init}	bar	80
Caliper mass (front / rear) *)	m_C	kg	0.75 / 0.4
Caliper diameter (front / rear) *)	d_C	mm	60 / 34
Caliper stiffness (front / rear) *)	c_B	N/m	3.5×10^7 / 1.07×10^7
Caliper dampening coefficient (front / rear) *)	k_B	Ns/m	9.5×10^5
Friction force (Coulomb) (front / rear) *)	F_C	N	350 / 150
Friction coefficient between brake pads and discs *)	μ_{PD}	-	0.43

In addition to the EH-BBW, the H-BBW should also be modelled. Due to the even higher complexity and the situation of confidential information, it was not possible to create an analytical model with adequate accuracy or performance. The only option would have been to use many simplifications and look-up tables instead of real mathematical formulae, which was not the intention of the research. For this reason, only the transfer function model is discussed in the next section. Due to the significantly shorter pipe lengths (compared to EH-BBW) and the higher dynamics of the directly driven corner actuators, only minor effects are to be expected.

Model validation and assessment

After creation of the models, their accuracy shall be investigated. Therefore, the simulation results of test bed (HIL), the transfer functions (TFs) and the analytical models (AMs) are compared, see Fig. 7 to Fig. 9.

Figure 7. Results of EH-BBW for a pressure step on the FL and RL corner

Figure 8. Results of EH-BBW for a saw tooth on the FL and RL corner

Figure 9. Results of EH-BBW for a sine wave on the FL and RL corner

It is evident from all the diagrams that there is a slight deviation between the target and actual values at the rear axle. In particular, the measured values at the brake system installed on the test bench remain below the actual demand, which is due to the internal control for brake pressure adjustment.

The plots show two results: i) both approaches are suitable to reproduce the behavior of the braking system, but ii) the analytical approach shows a better tracking of the reference values ('HIL') in all three test cases. Furthermore, the transfer function shows an undershoot for the ramp (see Fig. 8) and the step signal (see Fig. 9). If the behavior is transferred to real cases, this corresponds to a negative brake pressure, which is impossible. The analytical model, whose subcomponents form their values on the basis of mathematical approximations of the physical processes, can therefore not simulate undershoots and only falls back to their initial states, which gives a better emulation of the real behavior. In the appendix, the zoomed diagrams are shown with a larger scaling of the x -axis.

For an objective evaluation, the *Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)* of the brake pressure (p_{br}) (see eq. (6)) is calculated between the start (t_0) and end of the simulation (t_1). The sample time is set to $t_s = 1$ ms.

$$RMSE(p_{br}) = \sqrt{\frac{t_s}{t_1 - t_0} \sum_{t=t_0}^{t_1} [p_{br,Model}(t) - p_{br,HIL}(t)]^2} \quad (6)$$

Second, the *Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE)* is calculated to evaluate the amount of the RMSE in relation to the average brake pressure (\bar{p}_{br}). This gives the percentual deviation.

$$NRMSE(p_{br}) = \frac{RMSE(p_{br})}{\bar{p}_{br}} 100\% \quad (7)$$

The results of the KPI evaluation for one corner per axle are shown in the following table, restricted to the times shown in the right subplots in Fig. 8 to Fig. 10. The values of all corners and models in this period as well as for the entire simulation time are included in the appendix.

Table 4. Values of the KPI for EH-BBW for depicted manoeuver

		$RMSE(p_{br})$ [bar]		$NRMSE(p_{br})$ [%]	
		FL	RL	FL	RL
Step Response	AM	1.7999	2.0310	2.8154	3.6634
	TF	3.2899	2.7984	4.9943	4.8285
Saw Tooth	AM	1.8279	2.1745	7.1468	10.1025
	TF	2.9889	1.8882	11.3423	8.1446
Sine	AM	3.0227	2.8509	7.0824	7.7126
	TF	2.7130	1.8403	6.2050	4.7812

The data show that the analytical model is suitable for both ramp and pressure step maneuvers as they occur in normal braking situations. For transient sinusoidal signals, the performance is worse than for the transfer function due to the slower dynamics of the model components. Since a sinusoidal signal is quite uncommon in reality, these results should not matter too much. Furthermore, both models still show acceptable accuracy in most tests, with less than 10 % error.

In addition to the EH-BBW system, the same simulations were carried out with the hybrid BBW system, see Fig. 10 to Fig. 12. As before, the diagrams of the selected signals are shown enlarged in the appendix.

Figure 10. Results of H-BBW for a torque step on the FL and RL corner

Figure 11. Results of EH-BBW to a saw tooth on the FL and RL corner

Figure 12. Results of EH-BBW to a sine wave on the FL and RL corner

It should be mentioned that the hybrid system is controlled by torque instead of pressure demands. Therefore, the signals were normalized to the maximum amount and then multiplied with a gain to reach the torque that is equivalent to the pressure demands for the EH-BBW, see Fig. 10 to Fig. 12. Table 5 includes the exact RMSE and NRMSE values of the experiments. As for the EH-BBW, the full data set is included in the appendix. Since the H-BBW is torque-controlled, p_{br} in eq. (6) - (7) gets replaced by T_{br} .

Table 5. Values of the KPI for H-BBW for depicted manoeuvre

		$RMSE(T_{br})$ [Nm]		$NRMSE(T_{br})$ [%]	
		FL	RL	FL	RL
Step Response	TF	93.2653	44.2916	5.0430	5.92007
Saw Tooth	TF	61.0400	25.9400	6.8749	7.22197
Sine	TF	35.0132	20.3141	2.3694	3.3978

As already seen at EH-BBW, the transfer function can follow the signals quite well. Due to the architecture of the H-BBW with much

shorter line lengths between the EHAs and the EHBs at the front axle, the response time is even shorter than with the EH-BBW. On the other hand, there is a significant difference between the front and rear axle of the H-BBW: the RMSE values (see Table 5 and Table 7) for the rear axle are half the size or smaller than for the front axle. This is due to the actuation principle, as the electromechanical actuators on the rear brake caliper can act faster, so that the torque control is more precise. Nevertheless, the deviations (RMSE) seem to be quite high, but when looking at the normalized errors (NRMSE) it becomes clear that the values are lower than for EH-BBW, which means that the transfer function of the H-BBW has a higher accuracy.

Summary/Conclusions

This article deals with the setup, validation and comparison of simulation models for two brake-by-wire systems with different architectures. The results show that both the transfer function and the analytical model are able to simulate the behavior of the brake system as derived from real measurements on two hardware-in-the-loop test benches with only minor deviations. The analytical model offers the possibility to adapt the model in case of a planned part replacement, provided that the technical data is known. This is of great advantage for system development at a very early design stage without a prototype. Furthermore, it provides a good starting point for investigations in other disciplines, e.g. experiments on noise, vibration and harshness (NVH) phenomena, as partly presented in [24], where simple transfer functions do not have the required level of detail. On the other hand, the setup of such an analytical model is quite complex and time-consuming, so that an individual decision is required. Moreover, in many cases this technical data is not available. In the study conducted, this problem occurred with the hybrid brake-by-wire system. Due to technical difficulties, missing parameters and sensitive data, it was not possible to set up an analytical model as intended, but the results of the validation tests show that the accuracy of the transfer function is quite high, so that its suitability for benchmarking purposes or performance tests is nevertheless given. Once the unknown parameters of the electric drives, spindle gear and internal control are known, an analytical model can be set up for further investigations in the future.

Less complex is the approach of transfer function modelling. On the other hand, the description of the system behavior by a low-order formula allows only low predictions about the influence of technical changes, e.g. by replacing all valves by alternative parts with different dimensions, it is hard to say in which way the coefficients of the formula have to be changed to capture the changes in the system behavior. This has been shown in this article because identical corner brakes have different transfer functions and accuracies (RMSE, NRMSE).

For the electrohydraulic system, both approaches were processed and described in detail. In the subsequent validation tests, they showed good performance with different feasibility depending on the maneuver. Nevertheless, it can be stated that there is no doubt about their accuracy for further investigations on performance or even on brake control design.

Finally, some open points that were not part of the article will be discussed. Since some parameters and most parts of the internal pressure control algorithm of the EH-BBW system were not known in detail, some assumptions were necessary. These parameters and elements of the control algorithm offer potential for further improvements in accuracy. In particular, some material and

dimensional parameters were identified in parallel research activities for optimization in [24]. Furthermore, after adjustments to the discussed internal controls, the analytical model of the EH-BBW showed improved performance even in transient maneuvers.

Figure 13. Direct comparison of the analytic model's accuracy (EH-BBW) in transient sine maneuver with former [23] and adapted [24] control. The black solid line is the demand, while the black and grey dashed lines are the model output for FL and RL corner

Due to the unknown technical parameters of the H-BBW system, only the transfer function was part of the experiments in this article. In the future, system design investigations will be carried out to obtain the parameters needed for analytical modelling.

In all experiments and for both BBW systems, a by-wire operation was used, which means that the behavior and influence of the master cylinder or brake booster were not considered. In future applications (e.g. fail-safety tests, takeover scenarios, etc.), these parts must also be taken into account. Therefore, it is mandatory to extend the analytical model to include these parts. For the modelling of the transfer function, new test runs are needed in which the brake pedal is applied externally, e.g. by a brake robot. These points will be carried out by the authors for future research.

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Definitions/Abbreviations

BBW	brake-by-wire
EHB	electrohydraulic brake
EMB	electromechanical brake
EH-BBW	electrohydraulic brake-by-wire
H-BBW	hybrid brake-by-wire
TF	transfer function
AM	analytic model

Appendix

Figure 14. Results for EH-BBW response to a pressure ramp of 80 bar on the FL and RL corner (enlarged)

Figure 15. Results for EH-BBW response to a saw tooth of 80 bar on the FL and RL corner (enlarged)

Figure 16. Results for EH-BBW response to a pressure sine of 80 bar on the FL and RL corner (enlarged)

Table 6. Values of the KPIs for EH-BBW

		$RMSE(p_{br})$ [bar]				$NRMSE(p_{br})$ [%]			
		FL	FR	RL	RR	FL	FR	RL	RR
Time period starts at $t = t_0$ and ends at $t = t_f$ (period of one maneuver)									
Step Response	AM	1.7999	2.2120	2.0310	2.0551	2.8154	3.4719	3.6634	3.7069
	TF	3.2899	3.3601	2.7984	2.8276	4.9943	5.1611	4.8285	4.8903
Saw Tooth	AM	1.8279	2.2566	2.1745	2.0491	7.1468	8.8231	10.1025	9.5202
	TF	2.9889	3.0817	1.888	1.9212	11.3423	11.8327	8.1446	8.3061
Sine	AM	3.0227	3.1010	2.8509	2.7612	7.0824	7.2659	7.7126	7.4701
	TF	2.7130	2.7126	1.8403	1.8410	6.2050	6.2783	4.7812	4.7940
Time period starts at $t = T_0$ and $t = T_f$ (period of all maneuvers of the same kind)									
Step Response	AM	2.2923	2.4800	2.1459	2.0916	3.5856	3.8788	3.8707	3.7728
	TF	2.0775	2.1450	1.5657	1.5686	3.1538	3.2948	2.7016	2.7128
Saw Tooth	AM	1.7480	2.0170	1.5521	1.4528	6.8345	7.8864	7.2111	6.7497
	TF	2.5185	2.6361	1.5223	1.5615	9.5571	10.1218	6.5662	6.7508
Sine	AM	3.0516	3.1348	2.5829	2.5329	7.1502	7.3451	6.9878	6.8524
	TF	2.6495	2.7811	1.7163	1.7406	6.0599	6.4368	4.4592	4.5324

Figure 17. Results for H-BBW response to a pressure ramp of 80 bar on the FL and RL corner (enlarged)

Figure 18. Results for H-BBW response to a saw tooth of 80 bar on the FL and RL corner (enlarged)

Figure 19. Results for H-BBW response to a pressure sine of 80 bar on the FL and RL corner (enlarged)

Table 7. Values of the KPI for H-BBW

		$RMSE(T_{br})$ [Nm]				$NRMSE(T_{br})$ [%]			
		FL	FR	RL	RR	FL	FR	RL	RR
Time period starts at $t = t_0$ and ends at $t = t_l$ (period of one manoeuver)									
Step Response	TF	93.2653	94.5494	44.2916	43.9785	5.0430	5.1126	5.92007	5.8777
Saw Tooth	TF	61.0400	60.0928	25.9400	25.5362	6.8749	6.7684	7.22197	7.1089
Sine	TF	35.0132	36.9544	20.3141	18.1838	2.3694	2.5007	3.3978	3.041
Time period starts at $t = T_0$ and $t = T_l$ (period of all manoeuvres of the same kind)									
Step Response	TF	51.8553	55.9044	27.1915	24.7651	4.6106	4.97077	5.9763	5.4425
Saw Tooth	TF	46.8371	46.7770	19.6247	18.9096	9.3974	9.38557	9.7331	9.3776
Sine	TF	27.3292	29.7444	18.0588	16.4404	2.7421	2.98457	4.4790	4.0772